

Resolution Entropy In Quantum Mechanics and Born's Rule?

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be derived by assigning equal probability to all different partitions of an energy E among two particles (i.e. energy is conserved). These various distribution scenarios lead to many different partitions and hence uncertainty in which partition actually occurs in a given two particle collision.

We have argued before that quantum mechanics makes use of this idea of conservation (of both energy and momentum separately for a free particle) with partitions having the same weight, but the difference is that quantum mechanics introduces a second variable, t for energy and x for momentum, such that conservation appears naturally through orthogonal functions in these variables. In other words, there is a t and x resolution uncertainty introduced in this process which should be associated with a kind of entropy, albeit one which seems to be quite different from the usual thermodynamic entropy. This entropy, for example, is not additive and does not obey the first law of thermodynamics. For a bound state, however, it seems to obey the second law of thermodynamics, but some collisions may decrease this entropy depending on how it is calculated (as we show).

As a result, $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ have t and x resolutions in order to enforce conservation of E and p , but a given p may correspond to various E values and so there is a decoupling of the E and p resolutions. In a quantum bound state, however, the overall average energy is E_n and so one has $\exp(-iE_n t)$ which is orthogonal in time to $\exp(-iE_m t)$. Various momentum interactions occur in space and so the overall wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is consistent with $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$. This is equivalent to the classical relation for all energy levels. $W(x)$, however, has resolution entropy, i.e. crests and troughs, and one may ask what these signify? They represent the average resolution signature in space, but this signature is consistent with an average energy E_n at each x . In other words, $\exp(-iE_n t)$ is an orthogonal function in t for energy conservation and the corresponding $W_n(x)$ must be an orthogonal function (with $W_{n1}(x)$ etc) in space for energy conservation as well. What is the practical significance of this energy conservation? If one has a perturbation potential $V_1(x)$ which acts in space, it can affect $W_n(x)$ in such a way that $W_{n1}(x)$ is created with energy conservation enforced through the spatial resolution and $V_1(x)$. In other words, $\int dx W_{n1}^*(x) V_1(x) W_n(x)$ should pick the square root of the probability for a transition. Multiplying this value by its complex conjugate yields the probability for the transition, i.e. Born's Rule.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Entropy and Conservation of Energy

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, $\exp(-e/T)$, may be obtained by considering the maximum number of ways of distributing a total energy E among N particles with no bias (except that on average one has E/N energy). Alternatively, one may consider a two particle collision which conserves energy and note that one may partition the total energy in any way possible with the same probability. Thus, one may bring the global idea of maximum distribution of E among N particles to a specific two particle interaction using the idea of conservation of energy i.e.

$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ etc if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((1))

This holds for all combinations so $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ where $-1/T$ is a constant ((2)).

Quantum mechanics preserves this conservation idea for both momentum and energy. For example, for a free particle, $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)=\exp(ip_3x)\exp(ip_4x)$ (one dimension) if $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ and a similar result for $\exp(-iEt)$.

The Idea of Quantum Resolution

For a free particle, a given p does not tell one $E=pp/2m$ (or the relativistic value). Thus, x and t and $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are considered independently. For example, 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction are calculated only using $\exp(ipx)$ s.

We suggest that a second uncertainty or entropy exists due to the wavelength or period linked with $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. This entropy is completely different from the classical notion of entropy and we argue that one might not even need to use Shannon's entropy formula for it.

For example, in the literature (1), one often sees an expression for a bound state entropy (linked to spatial resolution) given by:

$$\text{Spatial entropy} = \int dx \ W^*(x)W(x) \ln W^*W \quad ((3))$$

A momentum entropy is also given by: $\int dp \ a^*(p)a(p)$ ((4)) where $W(x)=\sum$ over $p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

We suggest focusing on x and t resolution and suggest the following. Classsically, one has dx and dt which are in principle supposed to tend to 0. Nevertheless, one may choose nonzero minimum values of dx and dt which would suffice in a classical situation. As a first approximation, one may consider entropy to be given by Boltzmann's $-\ln(\text{number of states})$ i.e.

$$\text{Spatial entropy} = -k \ln (.5 \text{ hbar}/ (pdx)) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and Time entropy} = -k \ln (.5 \text{ hbar}/ (Edt)) \quad ((5b))$$

One might argue that the probability linked with a half wavelength is $C_1C_1 \sin(px)\sin(px)$ normalized to half a wavelength and that instead of giving a full weight to each dx in half a wavelength, one could give a weight $(C_1C_1 \sin(px)\sin(px))$. This would then give a little different result than ((5a)) and ((5b)). The point we wish to make is that such a resolution entropy differs from ((3)).

For a bound state, as E_n becomes high, at one point a half-wavelength and half period will match dx and dt and $\ln(1)=0$. At this point, there is no longer any quantum entropy and one has determinism. Given that a bound state spontaneously decays, the second law of thermodynamics seems to hold for the quantum bound state. Collisions of $\exp(ip_1x)$ with $\exp(ip_2x)$, however, lead to a total momentum of $\exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. Using ((5a)) one may see that spatial entropies do not add, i.e.:

$$\ln(1/p_1) + \ln(1/p_2) \neq \ln(1/(p_1+p_2)) \quad ((6))$$

Furthermore, if $p_1=p_2$, $-2 \ln(p)$ is the spatial resolution entropy before and $-\ln(2p)$ after. By adjusting the value of p , one may less spatial entropy in the combination p_1+p_2 .

Thus, the resolution entropy, which is purely quantum mechanical and linked to conservation of energy and momentum seems to be of a very different nature than entropy in classical thermodynamics.

The Quantum Bound State

The quantum bound state for $V(x)$ satisfies the classical energy conservation equation:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

for all energy levels. The quantum feature is the spatial resolution of crests and troughs in $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and in $\exp(-iEnt)$. Thus the spatial and time resolution entropies characterize or are a signature of the bound state W_n .

We note that $\exp(-iEnt)$ s are orthogonal in time, which is linked to time resolution. Given that one imposes the classical ((7)) using $\exp(ipx)$ s to signify momentum conserving collision with $V(x)$, then ((7)) is really an E_n constraint on the set of $\exp(ipx)$ s. In other words, if $\exp(-iEnt)$ is orthogonal in t , $W_n(x)$ should be orthogonal in x for consistency which is what occurs. As a result, the $W(x)$ crest-trough pattern (resolution pattern or entropy) ensures conservation of energy in a purely spatial calculation.

To see this in practice, consider $W_{n1}(x)$, $W_n(x)$ and a perturbation potential $V1(x)$. If $V1(x)$ is able to "knock" $W_n(x)$ into a higher energy level, i.e. n_1 , in a purely spatial manner then it must change the resolution pattern of $W_n(x)$. Given that $W_n(x)$ form a complete orthogonal basis: $V1(x)W_n(x) = \sum \text{over } n \ a_n W_n(x)$. Thus, one may find an overlap with $W_{n1}(x)$ which conserves energy and obtain a_n . It is energy conservation which results from this calculation because the $\exp(ipx)$ together with ((7)) ensure this. This is the non-classical feature of quantum mechanics, we argue, because ((7)) is purely classical. Given a_n , one may take $a_n^* a_n$ to obtain the probability, just as $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ yields 1 which is the classical $P(x)$.

Photon Absorption

In the case of photon absorption, $E_2 = E_1 + \hbar \omega$, so $\exp(-iE_2 t) = \exp(-iE_1 t)\exp(-i\hbar \omega t)$. For the momentum case, E_1 may have 0 momentum, so E_2 has $\exp(i\hbar \omega/c x)$ which matches $\exp(ikx)$ for the photon. Thus, the $W(x)$ crest-trough pattern is really the realization of $\exp(-iEnt)$ in space, we argue.

Quantum Resolution Entropy and Conservation for high E_n

In the high E_n limit, we have argued that the crest and trough base lengths match dx and so one does not need to use a statistical theory, i.e. quantum mechanics. In other words, one has

determinism, but the loss of resolution entropy means that one must enforce conservation by hand, because the resolution entropy of quantum mechanics is linked with this feature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum free particle wavefunctions (probabilities) $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ enforce conservation of momentum (as we have argued in a previous note), but at the same time introduce a non-thermodynamical entropy which we crudely estimate as $-\ln(\hbar/(\rho dx))$ and $-\ln(\hbar/(E dt))$, where dx and dt are tiny numbers which represent minimal values of dx and dt which would appear as $dx=0$, $dt=0$ in a classical scenario. We note that for a given p , one may have various E_n values and so $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iE_n t)$ are treated independently. This entropy differs from the usual Shannon's entropies for x and p using W^*W as $P(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ as $P(p)$.

Such does not seem to be the case for a bound state. A bound state with E_n has $\exp(-iE_n t)$ which enforces energy conservation in time. In space, various impulse hits between the single particle and $V(x)$ occur which conserve momentum, but overall on average one has E_n at each x . Thus, if $\exp(-iE_n t)$ is orthogonal in time, $W_n(x)$ should be orthogonal in space to enforce conservation of energy in space. This has a practical consideration because one may consider a perturbation potential $V_1(x)$ in space and combine it with $W_n(x)$ to obtain: $V_1(x)W_n(x) = \sum \text{over } n W_n(x)a_n$ because W_n 's form an orthogonal basis. The overlap with $W_{n_1}(x)$ means that energy is conserved and so a_n gives the weight which becomes $a_n^* a_n$ to find a classical probability, just as $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ yields a classical probability.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box